

AN EVALUATION OF INDIRAMMA HOUSING SCHEMES FOR LIG, MIG, AND WEAKER SECTIONS IN TELANGANA AND AP

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Abstract: Owning a House is one of the essential needs of mankind, along with food, clothing and education. The Housing Finance Companies (HFCs) as they are called today have stepped up their lending over the years contributing to the growth of the Housing Sector. The speedy development in housing and various housing activities has led to the growth of the Indian Housing Finance market. In this context, the present study is undertaken to analyze the phases of the Indian Housing Finance; present the schemes offered by the various categories of Housing Finance Institutions and to make a Region-wise and District-wise analysis of the Housing Finance provided by the various categories of the Institutions of Andhra Pradesh.

The Study is based on Secondary Data. The analysis of the schemes offered by the various State Government institutions financing housing in Andhra Pradesh is made Scheme-wise, District-wise and Region-wise. The data are analyzed with the help of percentages and ranks. HUDCO sanctions various schemes for housing and infrastructure activities in the States. A major portion of the total project cost is sanctioned as loan by HUDCO depending upon the progress of work. Housing Finance Companies are providing assistance for Housing Finance along with the other financial services like, Leasing and Credit, Financial Consultancy, Auto Finance, Car Finance, Personal Loans, Mortgage Loans and Insurance.

Telangana State Government is offering various schemes for Lower Income Group, Middle Income Group and Weaker Section of the society through various State Government Housing Corporations.

Keywords: housing finance, Housing Finance Companies (HFCs), HUDCO, Affordable housing schemes

Introduction

Owning a House is one of the essential needs of mankind, along with food, clothing and education. Housing acts as an important component for measuring socio-economic status of the people. The relevance of housing as social need has been long recognized; and this has influenced the innovations and inventions made by the mankind.

The importance of the Housing Sector can be judged from the fact that people consider house as the best investment and wants to invest their earnings in a house. The need for finance to purchase a house brought out specialized Housing Finance Institutions. The Housing Finance Companies (HFCs) as they are called today have stepped up their lending over the years contributing to the growth of the Housing Sector.

Housing Finance is a new concept in India compared to the other financial services that are available in the country. However, the speedy development in housing and various housing activities has

understandably led to the growth of the Indian Housing Finance market. As a result, a number of players have barged into the market.

In this context, the present study is undertaken in order to present the various phases of Indian Housing Finance and the schemes offered by The Housing Finance Institutions in Andhra Pradesh.

Review of Literature

1. Lee Bosher (2011) in his article “Household and Government Perception of Risk: Implications for the Appropriateness of Housing Provision in South India” highlights limited risk management strategies due to inadequate availability of insurance cover in the villages while ultimately illustrating the pitfalls of ill conceived and overly technocratic approaches to housing development.
2. Manoj P.K. (2010) in his article “Benchmarking Housing Finance Companies in India: strategies for enhanced operational efficiency and competitiveness” seeks to (i) make an overall review of the emergence of the institutional system for housing finance in India and to trace the broad pattern of its composition over the years, (ii) study the major problems and challenges faced by HFCs, particularly in comparison with CBs, the other major group, (iii) analyze the operational efficiency of the major HFCs and to benchmark them based on their relative operational efficiency, and (iv) suggest suitable strategies for enhanced operational efficiency of HFC’s in India.
3. Rao K.N. (2006) in his article “Housing Finance- A Global Perspective” mentioned that home loans have been registering exponential growth in India during the last six years. Easy liquidity conditions, low interest rates, availability of tax shelters on repayment of principal and interest surging demand from middle income group borrowers, lower regulatory capital, the comfort of tangible security have all collectively contributed to the spurt in home loans.
4. Brar, Jasmindeep Kaur and Paricha.S (2005) in their article “Performance of Housing Finance Companies” study the operational performance, and the financial performance of the selected institutions.
5. Praveen Gupta (2005) in his article “Housing Finance Companies- An insight into regulatory aspects” highlights some key regulatory aspects pertaining to Housing Finance Companies in the light of various directives and guidelines issued by the National Housing Bank, their regulatory authority in India.
6. M.Mahadeva (2004) in his article “Housing Problem and Public Action: Contained Incompatibility experience from a South Indian State” analyzed the nature and distribution of the housing problem in Karnataka and examined how the state has addressed this issue.

The review of literature points to the fact that though many studies have been made on Housing Finance, there is a gap with regard to an in-depth study of Scheme-wise, District-wise and Region-wise Housing Finance in Andhra Pradesh and hence the study to fill the research gap.

Objectives of the Study

The Objectives of the Study are to

- Analyze the phases of the Indian Housing Finance
- Present the schemes offered by the various categories of Housing Finance Institutions
- Make a Region-wise and District-wise analysis of the Housing Finance provided by the various categories of the Institutions of Andhra Pradesh Including Telangana state.

Methodology

- The Study is based on Secondary Data. The sources of Secondary Data are Annual Reports of Housing and Urban Development Corporation, National Housing Board and Andhra Pradesh State Government Websites.
- The analysis of the schemes offered by the various State Government institutions financing housing in Andhra Pradesh is made Scheme-wise, District-wise and Region-wise.
- The data are analyzed with the help of percentages and ranks.

Phases of Indian Housing Finance

The Housing Finance revolution in India can be divided into five distinct phases which are presented in Table I.

Table – 1

Phases of Indian Housing Finance

Phases	Period	Status
Phase I	Before 1970	Government domination
Phase II	1970-1980	HUDCO and HDFC established
Phase III	1980-1990	Establishment of NHB
Phase IV	1990-2000	Liberalization of interest rates
Phase V	2000 to Present	High Growth

Source: ISB, Indu Centre for Real Estate and Infrastructure

Earlier to the year 1970, the Government domination was more in Housing Finance. In the year 1970, Housing and Urban Development Corporation (HUDCO), a fully owned Government Corporation was established to finance various housing and urban infrastructure activities. In the year 1977, India's first private sector housing finance company viz., Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited (HDFC) came into existence. Since then, the Housing Finance in India has been flying high. With the establishment of National Housing Bank (NHB) in the year 1988, which is wholly owned subsidiary of RBI, Housing Finance Companies in India were regulated. In the years 1990-2000, interest rates of Housing Finance Companies were liberalized. From the year 2000 onwards, there is a high growth in Housing Finance in India.

Housing Finance Institutions in India: Schemes Offered

Currently, housing finance in India is provided to the public by the different groups of institutions viz., Scheduled Commercial Banks; Scheduled Co-operative Banks; Housing Finance Companies (with public deposits & without public deposits); and State Level Apex Housing Finance Societies. The same is presented in Table 2 along with the number of companies and schemes offered.

The Schemes of the various institutions offering Housing Finance are both direct and indirect housing finance and Housing Loans under priority sector. The Direct Housing Finance is for the

construction/purchase of houses by the individuals, repairs, alterations and additions to houses by the individuals. Indirect Housing Finance includes refinancing schemes/sponsored schemes. Housing Loans under Priority Sector consists of schemes for Housing and Hostel for SC and ST and Slum Clearance Scheme.

From the below table, it is clear that the number of companies offering Housing Finance Schemes under Scheduled Cooperative Banks is the highest with 53 companies followed by Scheduled Commercial Banks (43), Housing Finance Companies not to accept deposits (33) State Level Apex Housing Societies (25) and Housing Finance Companies accepting deposits (19). It is the banks, both Cooperative Banks and Commercial, which are playing a major role in Housing Finance Sector due to their vast spread of branches, reaching every nook and corner of the country.

Table – 2

Housing Finance Institutions in India: Schemes Offered

S.No.	Category of Institution	No. of Companies	Schemes
1	Scheduled Commercial Banks	43	Direct Housing Finance, Indirect Housing Finance, Housing loans under priority sector
2	Scheduled Co-operative Banks	53	Construction/purchase of houses by individuals, repairs alterations and additions to houses by individuals, schemes for housing & hostels for SC and ST, Slum clearance schemes
3	Housing Finance Companies (not accept deposits)	33	Direct and indirect housing finance
4	Housing Finance Companies (accept deposits)	19	Direct and indirect housing finance
5	State Level Apex Housing Societies	25	Construction/purchase of houses by individuals, repairs alterations and additions to houses by individuals, schemes for housing & hostels for SC and ST, Slum clearance schemes

Source: National Housing Bank Reports

Projects Sanctioned by HUDCO: State-wise Analysis

HUDCO sanction various schemes for housing and infrastructure activities in the States. The State-wise sanction of schemes, loan amount and dwelling units is presented in Table 3.

From the below Table, we can observe that, among all the states, Tamil Nadu took first place with 2257 schemes sanctioned followed by Andhra Pradesh with 2126 schemes and Karnataka with 1439 schemes reflecting upon the growing needs of the housing activities and infrastructure development of the respective states.

Table 3

State Wise Details of Projects Sanctioned by HUDCO

Sl. No	State/UT Name	No. of Schemes Sanctioned	Project Cost in crores Rs.	Loan sanctioned in crores	Loan released in crores	Dwelling Units		Plots
						UPGD	New	
	STATES							
1	A P & Telangana	2126	33496.06	13599.4	8448.43	144243	2305529	5687
2	Arunachal Pradesh	9	16.48	6.38	6.39	0	1822	0
3	Assam	190	1882.86	955.17	897.03	15536	40713	1926
4	Bihar	218	9716.64	2067.23	242.65	23032	81102	5740
5	Chhattisgarh	276	31812.44	3152.46	1066.47	314	97754	18573
6	Delhi	86	100488.70	7437.44	1086.06	0	19905	0
7	Goa	40	2853.72	2130.91	261.79	5983	1410	1526
8	Gujarat	1249	50145.32	8801.91	5547.7	58492	532698	8196
9	Haryana	376	4360.86	1645.72	1271.22	17437	92228	4987
10	Himachal Pradesh	183	2184.84	1119.09	1061.07	948	73647	1391
11	Jammu & Kashmir	118	4444.52	590.32	546.33	11123	12828	11330
12	Jharkhand	123	9995.22	3303.93	2202.62	10346	388185	2000
13	Karnataka	1439	48639.92	12823.76	9232.15	287596	1906560	35872
14	Kerala	1100	6649.48	3508.13	3118.42	99286	1156270	651
15	Madhya Pradesh	950	19256.22	5805.01	4154.24	9436	176221	140384
16	Maharashtra	1254	97828.08	13343.37	7404.88	51859	679756	18355
17	Manipur	39	280.59	148.63	140.51	385	14207	0
18	Meghalaya	35	555.15	368.58	297.37	291	15104	1
19	Mizoram	35	168.91	96.26	96.26	5150	6989	148
20	Nagaland	236	1250.39	886.86	858.37	29	22014	332
21	Odisha	456	12596.05	2510.11	1394.76	15283	261695	7147

22	Punjab	526	5713.90	2994.84	879.77	14864	103170	7169
23	Rajasthan	1156	16650.76	9529.76	6225.93	0	556100	204286
24	Sikkim	38	3268.32	415.85	246.72	3854	8985	0
25	Tamilnadu	2257	39894.89	13967.57	9735.85	324651	1075632	161749
26	Tripura	37	268.02	89.58	70.82	1909	5661	1
27	Uttar Pradesh	1298	30837.18	9074.49	5405.25	32546	653690	65928
28	Uttarakhand	105	1069.89	575.95	318.71	3506	51959	560
29	West Bengal	337	12702.58	366.37	3327.24	3020900	194796	5346

UNION TERRITORY

30	A & N Islands	16	25.86	13.21	10.91	0	534	0
31	Chandigarh	78	2066.94	203.50	171.16	0	28036	8045
32	Dadar Nagar Haveli	2	0.35	0.25	0.00	45	42	0
33	Puducherry	55	896.77	670.71	190.36	0	11860	0
	TOTAL	16443	552017.91	125502.75	75737.44	4159044	10577102	717330

Source: Annual Reports HUDCO

A major portion of the total project cost is sanctioned as loan by HUDCO depending upon the progress of work. The sanction of the loan depends not only on the project cost but also on the guarantee of the State Government towards borrowings.

The loans sanctioned for up-gradation of dwelling units is highest in case of West Bengal followed by Tamilnadu, Karnataka, and Andhra Pradesh whereas, for the new dwelling units, it is Andhra Pradesh which ranked first followed by Karnataka, Kerala and Tamilnadu. The demand for Housing Loans for plots is highest in case of Rajasthan followed by Tamilnadu and Maharashtra.

Housing Finance in Andhra Pradesh & Telangana State

The growing Housing Finance need in Andhra Pradesh is met by the various institutions. In Andhra Pradesh, there are 63 Housing Finance Institutions of which, 17 Finance Institutions are registered with National Housing Bank. The National Housing Bank (NHB) is a state owned bank and Regulation Authority in India created on July 8, 1988 u/s 6 of the National Housing Bank Act (1987). The institution, owned by the Reserve Bank of India, was established to promote private real estate acquisition. All Housing Finance Companies must register with National Housing Bank.

Here is the list of Housing Finance Companies in Andhra Pradesh which are registered with NHB. From the below Table, we can observe that the Housing Finance Companies are providing assistance for Housing Finance along with the other financial services like, Leasing and Credit, Financial Consultancy, Auto Finance, Car Finance, Personal Loans, Mortgage Loans and Insurance. Of the 17 Finance Institutions registered with NHB, 10 Finance Companies are providing only Housing Finance services rest of the 7 Finance Institutions are offering other services along with Housing Finance.

Table 4
Housing Finance in Andhra Pradesh

S.No	Name of the Institution	Services
1	HDFC	Housing Finance, Bank, Financing Leasing and Credit Organization
2	Dewan Housing Finance Corporation Limited	Housing Finance, Financing Leasing and Credit Organization, Investment Consultant
3	Bank of Maharashtra	Housing Finance, Bank, ATM
4	Bank of Baroda	Housing Finance, Bank, ATM
5	LIC Housing Finance Limited	Housing Finance, Financing Leasing and Credit Organization
6	RepcO Home Finance Limited	Housing Finance
7	ICICI Home Limited	Housing Finance, ATM, Personal Loans, Car Finance
8	Indiabulls Housing Finance Limited	Housing Finance
9	Canfin Homes Limited	Housing Finance
10	Sundaram Bnp Paribas Home Finance Limited	Housing Finance, Consultant, Financial Leasing and Credit Organization
11	DHFL	Housing Finance
12	National Trust Housing Finance Limited	Housing Finance, consultant, Financial Leasing and credit Organization
13	GIC Housing Finance Limited	Housing Finance

14	SBI	Housing Finance, Banks, ATM
15	GE Home Loan Agent Property	Housing Finance
16	Manipal Housing Finance Syndicate	Housing Finance
17	Ind Bank Housing Ltd	Housing Finance

Source: www. Indiacom.com

The above mentioned Housing Finance Companies are focusing more on upper middle class and creamy layer. Andhra Pradesh State Government is focusing on the weaker sections of the society through its housing finance schemes.

State Government Housing Corporations in Andhra Pradesh: Schemes offered

In Andhra Pradesh, Housing Finance is provided by the various institutions viz., Institutions registered with NHB (17), Institutions not registered with NHB (46) and Housing Corporations fully owned by State Government (4). The schemes offered by the State Government Housing Corporations in Andhra Pradesh are provided in Table-5 below.

Table – 5

Andhra Pradesh State Government Housing Corporation: Schemes offered

Name of the Institution	Incorporated Year	Schemes
A.P. Housing Board	1 st July 1960	Integrated/Composite Housing Schemes
A.P. Housefed	13 th December 1968	L.I.G.H.-I&II, M.I.G.H-I&II, Repairs and Extensions
Andhra Pradesh State Housing Corporation	5 th July 1979	Indiramma, Flood Housing, Indira Awas Yojana, Beedi Workers Housing in Rural and Urban areas, Integrated Housing and Slum Development Programs, Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission, Weavers Work Shed, Other Schemes
A.P. Rajiv Swagruha Corporation Limited	August, 2007	Housing Schemes for moderate income group

Source: A.P. State Government Websites

From the above Table, it is observed that Andhra Pradesh State Government is offering various schemes for Lower Income Group, Middle Income Group and Weaker Section of the society through various Housing Corporations. The State Government Housing Corporations are Andhra Pradesh Housing Board, Andhra Pradesh Housefed, Andhra Pradesh State Housing Corporation and Andhra Pradesh

Rajiv Swagruha Corporation Limited. Now a detailed study of these Government Corporation Schemes is made.

Andhra Pradesh Housing Board: Schemes Offered

A.P Housing Board is the oldest among all the State Government Housing Corporations. A.P. Housing Board earlier known as City Improvement Board was established on 1st July 1960. The various Schemes offered by the Andhra Pradesh Housing Board, the first State Government Housing Corporation in Andhra Pradesh is presented in Table-6

Table 6:

Andhra Pradesh Housing Board: Schemes Offered

Sl. No	Name of the District	SFC	HIG	MIG	LIG	EWS	CIB	RGK	Total	Rank
I	Telangana Region									
1	Mahabubnagar		26	327	841	109		384	1687	16
2	Nalgonda	-	14	419	1194	286	-	-	1913	13
3	Ranga Reddy	66	3563	6499	8828	1749	-	25747	46452	1
4	Hyderabad	1506	86	2784	7254	2647	2324	-	16601	2
5	Medak	-	-	775	1777	--	-	-	2552	9
6	Nizamabad	-	20	1454	1215	-	-	992	3681	3
7	Adilabad	-	-	306	770	208	-	-	1284	19
8	Warangal	-	28	962	1561	24	-	512	3087	5
9	Karimnagar	-	-	675	793	167	-	-	1635	17
10	Khammam	-	-	79	16	187	-	-	282	23
	Total	1572	3737	14280	24249	5377	2324	27635	79174	I
II	Rayalaseema Region									
11	Kurnool	-	106	827	929	-	-	120	1982	12
12	Ananthapur	-	16	718	1068	-	-	-	1802	15
13	Cuddapah	-	45	284	815	-	-	1248	2392	10
14	Chittoor	-	12	179	279	-	-	-	470	22
	Total	-	173	2008	3091	-	-	1368	6640	III
III	Andhra Region									
15	Nellore	-	179	400	1336	100	-	704	2719	8
16	East Godavari	-	131	589	1120	60	-	-	1900	14
17	West Godavari	-	110	834	1616	245	-	280	3085	6
18	Krishna	-	126	1767	120	-	-	-	12013	11
19	Guntur	-	49	961	138	-	-	1888	3036	7
20	Prakasam	-	-	389	250	-	-	-	639	21

21	Vizayanagarm	-	-	414	579	-	-	-	993	20
22	Srikakulam	-	-	797	677	-	-	-	1474	18
23	Visakhapatnam	-	169	1823	1417	-	-	-	3409	4
	Total	-	764	7974	7253	405	-	2872	19268	II
	Grand Total	1572	4680	24262	34593	5782	2324	31875	105088	

Source: A.P. Housing Board Website

The above Table shows the details of houses constructed and allotted for different districts in Andhra Pradesh since its inception. From the Table, it is observed that, it is providing different housing schemes namely, SFS (Self Finance Scheme), HIG (Higher Income Group) MIG (Middle Income Group), LIG (Lower Income Group), EWS (Economically Weaker Sections) and CIB (City Improvement Board) and RGK (Rajiv Gruhakalpa).

- Scheme-wise analysis reveals that the number of houses constructed is highest in Lower Income Group (34593) and under Rajiv Gruha Kalpa (31875).
- District-wise analysis shows that Ranga Reddy District took first place in the total number of houses constructed with 46452 houses followed by Hyderabad (16601) and Nizamabad (3681).
- As per the Region-wise analysis, Telangana Region ranked one (79174 Houses) on an overall basis followed by Andhra (19268) and Rayalaseema (6640) Region.
- An interesting feature is that, in Telangana Region, Rajiv Gruha Kalpa Scheme is popular whereas in Rayalaseema, Lower Income Group Schemes are popular and in Andhra Region, popularity is for Middle Income Group Schemes.

Andhra Pradesh Housefed: Schemes offered

A.P. Housefed was registered as an Apex Cooperative Federation under the Andhra Pradesh Cooperative Societies Act (A.P.C.S), 7 of 1964 on 13.12.1966 and started functioning since 1968. Its area of operation is the entire State of Andhra Pradesh. As on today, it has got 1,438 Primary Societies as Members, of which 820 are borrowing members.

The main objective of the A.P. Housefed is to advance loans to the members of the Primary Housing Societies in the State of Andhra Pradesh by availing loans from Life Insurance Corporation of India, Mumbai. The loans availed from the LIC of India are not guaranteed by the Government of A.P.

The A.P. Housefed is financing loans to the members of the affiliated Primary Cooperative Housing Societies in the State of Andhra Pradesh under 7 Schemes viz., L.I.G.H.-I and II; M.I.G.H and H.I.G.H-I, II and III; and Repairs and Extensions.

Andhra Pradesh State Housing Corporation Limited (APSHCL): Schemes Offered

A.P. State Housing Corporation Limited (APSHCL) was incorporated on 5th July 1979 under Companies Act. APSHCL aims to bring dignity to each and every below poverty line family by assisting them, both financially and technically, for construction of permanent (Pucca) houses. APSHCL is implementing various schemes viz., Indiramma, Rachabanda, Flood Housing and Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY) in rural areas; Beedi Workers Housing in Rural and Urban areas; Integrated Housing and Slum Development Program (IHSDP) and Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission (JNNURM).

Andhra Pradesh Government has taken a decision to take up the development of model villages and towns with an intention to saturate certain identified basic needs of the people and the village/town infrastructure in an integrated and focused manner. This is planned to be achieved in a period of 3

years. This new model of development is named as **Indiramma** (Integrated Novel Development in Rural areas and Model municipal areas)

The aim of Indiramma program is to provide in every village pucca houses, drinking water supply, individual sanitary latrines, drainages, power supply to every households, road facilities for transportation, pension to eligible old age persons, weavers, widows and disabled, primary education to all, special nutrition to adolescent girls/pregnant and lactating women and better health facilities in all the villages over a period of three years in a saturation mode, to improve the living standards of the people significantly.

Indiramma Scheme is the major activity of the APSHCL which is offered under three phases as provided in the Tables below.

- From the below Table, it is observed that among all the schemes, number of houses constructed is highest in Rural including IAY Scheme with 89.13 % of the total followed by Urban (9.60 %) and Flood Housing Schemes (1.26%).
- Among all the districts, Ananthapur district took 1st place in the total number of houses allotted with 1,33,899 houses and Cuddapah and Visakhapatnam are placed 2nd and 3rd places with 1,11,614 and 1,09,912 houses allotted respectively.
- According to Region-wise analysis, Andhra Region was in the 1st place with 777817 houses followed by Telangana Region (738996) and Rayalaseema Region (459208). As far as Rural including IAY and Flood Housing Schemes are concerned, it is Telangana Region which topped the list. Rayalaseema is in the last position with regard to all the schemes under Indiramma Phase – I Program.

Table – 7

Indiramma Phase – I: Region-wise and District-wise Analysis of Houses Allotted Under Various Schemes during 2006 - 07

Sl. No.	District	Urban	Rural including IAY	Flood Housing	Total
I	Telangana Region				
1	Mahabubnagar	3939	97428	0	101367
2	Ranga Reddy	5634	35816	151	41331
3	Hyderabad	0	0	0	0
4	Medak	6943	61263	1979	73185
5	Nizamabad	7037	51378	5678	64093
6	Adilabad	11575	80911	939	93425
7	Karimnagar	10697	54766	127	65590
8	Warangal	10256	88487	2681	101424
9	Khammam	7297	96830	1263	105390
10	Nalgonda	4306	89248	365	93191
	Total	67684	656127	13183	738996
II	Royalaseema Region				
11	Chittur	11704	92281	0	103985
12	Cuddapah	8457	103157	0	111614
13	Ananthapur	10093	123806	0	133899
14	Kurnool	13711	95999	0	109710
	Total	43965	415243	0	459208
III	Andhra Region				
15	Srikakulam	5922	69096	1875	76893
16	Vizayanagaram	10362	67493	1755	79610
17	Visakhapatnam	5134	102989	1789	109912
18	East Godavari	14558	8391	5230	102879
19	West Godavari	13641	81120	1095	95856
20	Krishna	6287	60519	00	66806
21	Guntur	5179	71723	00	76902
22	Prakasham	4956	77296	19	82271
23	Nellore	12202	75486	00	86688
	Total	78241	614113	11763	777817
	Grand Total	189620	1760183	24946	1974749
	% to Total	(9.60)	89.13 %	1.26 %	100 %

Source: APSHC website

Table – 8
Indiramma Phase – II: District wise allotment

S/No	District	Urban		Rural		Total	Rank
		No. of Municipalities	No. of Houses	No. of Panchayats	No. of Houses		
I	Telangana Region						
1	Mahabubnagar	40	6308	508	155936	162244	2
2	Ranga Reddy	148	3344	248	28193	31537	21
3	Hyderabad	0	0	0	0	0	23
4	Medak	63	11548	341	92244	103792	15
5	Nizamabad	57	10635	228	59177	69812	19
6	Adilabad	80	16765	347	102858	119623	11
7	Karimnagar	69	17540	451	77089	94629	17
8	Warangal	30	11811	414	119207	131018	8
9	Khammam	68	13343	278	125804	139147	6
10	Nalgonda	46	8982	456	131416	140398	4
	Total	601	100276	3271	891924	992200	II
II	Royalaseema Region						
11	Chittoor	85	19692	534	125100	144792	7
12	Cuddapah	80	12465	315	99943	112408	12
13	Ananthapur	108	33015	363	181595	214610	1
14	Kurnool	63	12847	339	130107	142954	5
	Total	336	78019	1551	536745	614764	III
III	Andhra Region						
15	Srikakulam	42	7286	404	75631	82917	18
16	Vizianagarma	43	14660	323	114157	128817	10
17	Vishakhapatnam	20	3405	347	114727	118126	9
18	East Godavari	74	13559	352	148604	162163	3
19	West Godavari	93	16872	297	95356	112228	14
20	Krishna	52	8792	374	55679	64471	20
21	Guntur	134	140183	358	87765	101948	16
22	Prakasam	42	6555	380	73668	80223	19
23	Nellore	50	15722	370	97582	113304	13

	Total	550	227034	3205	863169	1090203	I
	Grand Total	1487	279329 (10.86%)	8037	2291832 (89.14%)	2571161	

Source: APSHC Website

Table - 9

Indiramma Phase – III: Stages of Beneficiaries Houses as on 16-10-2012

S.N o.	District	Reg.	NS	BBL	BL	LL	RL	RC	ISL	Total
I	Telangana Region									
1	Mahabubnagar	2308	76853	4418	12172	3433	9038	43099	6882	155895
2	Ranga Reddy	1113	19456	3519	4625	1433	1979	32293	4763	68158
3	Hyderabad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Medak	3072	44224	4107	6477	3786	3102	27439	5012	94147
5	Nizamabad	1680	28624	931	1548	819	748	9589	3877	46136
6	Adilabad	585	22046	5261	7251	3792	8156	29380	1793	77679
7	Karimnagar	859	23074	1437	2793	937	1384	17644	4448	51717
8	Warangal	1659	53363	6059	6014	2989	5320	36553	6670	116968
9	Khammam	565	33275	1825	3732	1186	4210	31925	4025	80178
10	Nalgonda	4111	39010	1865	5886	1584	4118	28728	7773	88964
	Total	15952	339925	29782	50498	19959	38055	256650	38361	779842
II	Rayalaseema Region									
11	Chittor	5970	33547	1676	7092	678	3984	55066	6701	108744
12	Kadapa	2693	13703	600	4300	303	1059	17320	7555	44840
13	Ananthapur	11308	23858	6755	8020	1305	7117	34070	10374	91499
14	Kurnool	6055	36481	2545	4528	1187	3348	33220	14400	95709
	Total	26026	107589	11576	23940	3473	15508	139676	39030	340792
III	Andhra Region									
15	Srikakulam	1942	40385	1135	2998	1084	2028	31401	2188	81219
16	Vizayanagara	1857	44079	1346	5544	1840	2897	40123	3877	99706

17	Visakhapatnam	686	37837	2192	4290	2296	5250	40287	5433	97585
18	East Godavari	2651	32787	2684	1775	561	2169	27185	13868	81029
19	West Godavari	2149	15524	595	950	268	819	15861	9978	43995
20	Krishna	11902	18912	468	1067	364	1073	16376	4903	43163
21	Guntur	2003	24288	1092	1844	694	1139	23336	8940	61333
22	Prakasam	1531	27613	688	1989	620	1154	19044	5750	56858
23	Nellore	1647	24287	969	1733	441	871	19974	3280	51555
	Total	26368	265712	11169	22190	8168	17400	233587	58271	616443
	Grand Total	68346	713316	52167	96628	31600	70963	629913	142490	1737077
		3.93%	41.06%	3.00%	5.56%	1.81%	4.08%	36.26%	8.20%	

Source: A.P. State Housing Corporation website

Under Indiramma Phase – II Program, the total number of houses allotted for rural area is 89.14 per cent of the total houses allotted emphasizing the fact that rural areas were given top priority.

District-wise Analysis shows that, Ananthapur district took 1st place in the total number of houses allotted with 214610 houses and Mahabubnagar and East Godavari are placed 2nd and 3rd with 162224 and 162163 houses allotted respectively.

As per the Region-wise Analysis, Andhra Region (1090203) ranks first followed by Telangana (992200) and Rayalaseema Region (614764) in absolute terms. A noteworthy feature is that Telangana Region ranked first in the number of houses allotted in rural area and Andhra Region occupied the first place as far as the number of houses allotted in urban area. Rayalaseema Region ranked last in respect of the number of houses allotted in both, urban and rural areas as the number of districts is less.

District-wise Analysis shows that, Mahabubnagar took 1st place with 155895 houses and Warangal and Chittoor are placed 2nd and 3rd places with 116968 and 108744 houses respectively. As per the Region-wise Analysis, Telangana Region (779842) ranks first followed by Andhra (616443) and Rayalaseema Region (340792) in absolute terms. As far as registration of houses is concerned Andhra Region (26368) occupies first position followed by Rayalaseema (26026) and Telangana (15952).

Andhra Pradesh Rajiv Swagruha Corporation: Rajiv Swagruha Scheme

Government launched this program in 2007 for providing affordable housing to the moderate income group for implementation in all Municipalities and Municipal Corporations in the state. The main objective of Rajiv Swagruha Program is to make available the houses/flats to the moderate income group at cost 25% less than the prevailing market rate with best quality of construction and other infrastructure facilities. The details of places, number of units and project cost as on 2012 are given below is Table- 10.

Table – 10

Andhra Pradesh Rajiv Swagruha Corporation Limited: Number of Units and Project Cost as on 2012

S.No	Place	No. of Units	Project Cost (Rs. in Crores)	Rank (on the basis of No. of Units)
1	Chandanagar	1140	132	23
2	Pocharam	2604	405	9
3	Bandlaguda	2970	460	8
4	Kondapur	1736	407	15
5	Ananthapur	1134	170	25
6	Vetapalem (Chirala)	427	48	35
7	Nellore	1249	185	21
8	Bachupalli-I (39 & 40)	3517	760	6
9	Gajularamaram	2520	650	10
10	Mahabubnagar	1134	122	25
11	Kakinada	1664	285	16
12	Nizamabad	1140	174	23
13	Jawaharnagar	6214	1000	3
14	Bachupalli-II	2000	650	12
15	Adilabad	963	130	26
16	Yendada (VSP)	3588	1030	5
17	Nalgonda	458	65	34
18	Tandur (R.R. Dist.)	761	110	29
19	Vizag (Nadipur)	17000	5000	1
20	Etcherla (Srikakulam)	1461	225	18
21	Karimnagar	7350	1000	2
22	Narasaraopet	672	70	30
23	Ongole-I (Flats)	1548	120	17
24	Srikalahasthi	357	50	36
25	Tirupathi	1332	230	20
26	Rajampet	168	38	38

27	Rayachoti (KDP)	480	85	32
28	Khammam	1836	262	14
29	Chandanagar-II (Arambh)	1344	760	19
30	Munaganur	2000	380	12
31	Bahadurpalli	5400	1190	4
32	Kamareddy	580	85	31
33	Vikarabad	1200	175	22
34	Gadwal	906	155	27
35	Ramagundam	176	40	37
36	Boduppal	3068	665	7
37	Eluru	900	140	28
38	Nuzividu	468	55	33
39	Anakaplli	2008	340	11
40	Proddutur	488	40	31
		85961	17866	

Source: A.P. Swagraha Corporation Limited Website

From the above Table, it is observed that among all the places, Vizag took 1st place in the total number of units allotted with 17000 units and Karimnagar and Jawaharnagar are placed 2nd and 3rd with 7350 and 6214 units allotted respectively.

Conclusion

Investment in house is considered as the best option and the speedy development in housing and various housing activities has led to the growth of the India Housing Finance Market. The Government domination in housing finance has been reduced since 1970 and at present there is a high growth in the housing sector. The establishment of NHB has led to the regulation of the housing finance in India. Banks play a major role in Housing Finance Sector due to the vast spread of their branches reaching every nook and corner of the country. In Andhra Pradesh, the growing housing finance need is met by the various State Government Housing Corporations namely, A.P.Housing Board, A.P. Housefed, Andhra Pradesh State Housing Corporation and A.P. Rajiv Swagraha Corporation Limited by offering various housing finance schemes.

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